

A Comparison of Estimated and Measured Precast Segment Liner Loads Developed During Construction of twin EPB TBM Tunnels in Seattle

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ABSTRACT

Design liner loads are commonly estimated using a variety of closed-form analytical methods as well as numerical (2D or 3D finite element / finite difference) modeling. A number of assumptions are made during liner load assessment about material parameters, including elastic modulus, shear strength, Poisson's ratio, coefficient of lateral earth pressure, etc. In addition, estimates of pre-convergence during pressure-balance TBM tunneling are made, but with limited understanding of actual magnitudes. Assumptions about pre-convergence play a significant role in liner loads. In this paper, data from strain gages installed in two rings of segmental lining on the Seattle Sound Transit Northlink tunnel project is analyzed during the final state of geostatic loading in varying geologies along the glacially-deposited alignment. Commonly used numerical modeling methodologies are employed to predict liner loading. The comparison of experimental and model results show that when using assumptions of pre-convergence, the numerical modeling liner loads prediction and the measured bending moments show a closer correlation than when pre-convergence is not assumed. The measured thrust forces are significantly lower than the no pre-convergence model, indicating that this methodology can be unconservative in regards to the N-M capacity envelope.

Key words: Segmental lining design, Closed shield TBMs, Convergence confinement method, Twin tunnels.

1. INTRODUCTION

An age old challenge in tunnel design is the estimation of structural liner loads. Convergence-confinement principles illustrate the load sharing that occurs between ground and structural support, and that pre-convergence reduces the load supported by the liner. The method of excavation plays a critical role in pre-convergence and therefore liner loading. Conventional excavation methods, if even for a brief period of time, provide no counter stresses, i.e., the internal pressure is zero. Pre-convergence and ground self-support through arching can be significant. The resulting liner loading may only be a fraction of the overburden.

Pressure balance TBM tunneling, on the other hand, purposely applies counter pressures on the order of the in-situ geostatic stresses. The current focus on maintaining face, shield annulus and grout pressures, and the corresponding near zero deformations observed on most pressure balance tunnel

projects, suggests there may be very little pre-convergence prior to segmental liner erection. Segmental liner loading data from pressure balance TBM projects would help to understand this.

Further to liner loading, the longitudinal joints in segmental liners have a somewhat unclear influence on ground-structure interaction and liner forces. Muir Wood (1975) proposed an empirical liner stiffness reduction based on the number of longitudinal joints. This is commonly used in practice to estimate segmental lining stiffness. Of course, the influence of longitudinal joints can be addressed more mechanistically through finite element modeling. But model results require measurements for validation.

In this paper, data from strain gages installed in segmental lining rings on the Seattle Sound Transit Northlink tunnel project (Frank et al. 2015) are analyzed during the final state of geostatic loading in varying geologies along the glacially-deposited alignment. Commonly used numerical modeling methodologies are employed to predict liner loading. The experimental and model results are compared.

2. PROJECT BACKGROUND

The Northgate link extension project includes 5.6 km of twin bored tunnels and 23 cross passages, and is expected to be completed in 2018. The tunnels run north from the University of Washington to the Maple Leaf portal in north Seattle. The twin bored tunnels were constructed using two EPB TBMs each with an excavation diameter of 6.64 m and supported in a single pass, gasketed segmental lining, 25 cm thick, and an extrados diameter of 6.25 m. Each ring is composed of four full size segments and key and counter key segments. The nominal ring width was 1.5 m, and the universal ring had an overall ring taper of 69.9 mm. The prefabricated segment design concrete strength was 55 MPa, with realized strengths closer to 67 MPa on average. The segments were reinforced with wire mesh with primary reinforcement bars D14.

The geology of the area through which the tunnels were constructed consists of complex and highly variable interlayered glacial and non-glacial soil deposits. As part of the geotechnical baseline work, the geological units were grouped into engineering soil units (ESU) based on their behavioral characteristics. All tunnel excavation was conducted in the following glacially over ridden ESUs; till and till-like deposits (TLD), cohesionless sand and gravel (CSG), cohesionless silt and fine sand (CSF) and cohesive clays and silts (CCS). Figure 1 shows the variable geological conditions found at the two cross section discussed in this paper. Table 1 summarizes geotechnical properties of the different ESUs.

Figure 1. On the left the Northgate link geological cross section 1 at station 1290+10, on the right cross section 2 at station 1327+70

Table 1. Geotechnical properties according to engineering soil units encountered in the Northgate link project.

Engineering Soil Units (ESU)	Unit Weight [kN/m ³]	Effective Friction Angle ϕ' [deg]	Cohesion Intercept c' [kPa]	Undrained Shear Strength S_u [kPa]	At-Rest Earth Pressure Coefficient K_0	Elastic Modulus E [MPa]
Recent Granular Deposits (RGD)	19.5	34	0	N/A	0.5	75-120
Cohesionless Sand and Gravel (CSG)	20.1	39	0	N/A	0.6	230-315
Cohesive Clay and Silt (CCS)	19.6	30	120	340	1.5	200-305
Cohesionless Silt and Fine Sand (CSF)	20.1	38	0	N/A	0.6	230-260
Till and Till Like Deposits (TLD)	20.1	42	0	N/A	1.5	600-950

3. INSTRUMENTATION AND MONITORING

Selected segments were instrumented with vibrating wire strain gages. Data from two locations or cross-sections are presented in this paper. Within each selected ring, three segments were instrumented – two full-size segments plus a key or counter key. Each instrumented segment was outfitted with a set of two vibrating wire strain gauges welded to the reinforcement cage, one at the intrados and one at the extrados. The strain gauges were installed in a slightly asymmetrical configuration due to limitations in the casting process (Figure 2b). The intrados strain gauge center axis depth from the segment extrados is 58 mm as the strain gauge is installed on #3 rebar (9.5 mm) welded to the underside of the longitudinal 14 mm diameter (i.e., away from the intrados concrete face) rebar welded to the primary reinforcement (14 mm diameter), and minimum clearance is 25 mm. The extrados sister bar was installed on the exterior of the longitudinal reinforcement resulting in a depth of approximately 37 mm for the extrados strain gauge center axis.

The strain gages measure circumferential strain. From these two measurements, and knowing the geometry with respect to the segment neutral axis, the thrust force and bending moment can be calculated. The sign convention of the thrust forces and bending moments is positive for compressive thrust force, and positive for bending moment when the segment intrados is in tension (figure 2d). The strain gages were part of a wireless sensing system developed by Phase IV Engineering (Boulder, Colorado). The layout, implementation and recording program was developed in cooperation between the tunnel contractor JCM Northlink and designer L-7 Services (based in Golden, Colorado). Collection of the strain gauge readings required passing a flat panel RFID reading unit within 30 cm of the concrete surface in the vicinity of the embedded sensor. The monitoring schedule included an initial zero strain reading after the welding of the sister bars, and prior to casting, followed by readings every two weeks after segment installation.

Figure 2. a) Cross section of a typical instrumented ring, with the instrumented segments marked A, B & C. b) Segment cross section at strain gage location (dimensions in mm). c) Strain gage location on a typical segment plan view d) Sign convention for bending moments and thrust force.

4. CALCULATION MODELS USED

Two analysis approaches were investigated using 2D plane strain FEA. The first was a 'wished into place' approach where no pre-convergence or ground relaxation was allowed prior to liner installation. The second approach allowed for pre-convergence according to convergence-confinement theory. The 2D numerical modeling calculations were carried out using the FEA software GTS NX (Midas Ltd).

Modeling the liner-ground interaction with 2D plane strain analysis requires assumptions to simulate the effects of the 3D tunneling process. This is accomplished with the well-known convergence confinement method (CCM) based on the work of Panet (1982), Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) and others. The allowance of pre-convergence prior to liner placement accomplished through the CCM is widely used for conventional tunneling; however, in most design processes involving pressurized shield tunneling projects, pre-convergence is often neglected. The rationale is that pressure at the face of the

excavation reduces the pre-convergence, and that the assumption of zero pre-convergence yields more conservative (higher) lining forces.

This issue is examined in more detail here in the case of twin bored tunnels and low face pressure. To account for the pressure applied by the TBM at the face and around the shield, the convergence u_{ro} is calculated using CCM equations employing the effective machine pressure p'_i . The maximum convergence, well back from the face, is given in equation 1 by Hoek (2007) for an isotropic stress field where the internal support pressure is set equal to the TBM effective pressure p'_i at springline. p'_i is the magnitude of springline chamber pressure above and beyond the geostatic water pressure.

$$u_{max} = \frac{r_0(1+\nu)}{E} \left[2(1-\nu)(p'_0 - p'_{cr}) \left(\frac{r_p}{r_0} \right)^2 - (1-2\nu)(p'_0 - p'_i) \right] \quad (1)$$

Here, r_0 is the tunnel radius, p'_0 is the effective stress, r_p is the plastic radius and p'_{cr} is the critical support pressure, defined as the internal support pressure required such that no soil failure (plastic deformation) occurs (Hoek 2007). The pre-convergence at the location of lining installation can then be obtained according to the longitudinal displacement profile (LDP) of Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) in equation 2.

$$u(x) = u_{max} \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{u_f}{u_{max}} \right) e^{-\left(\frac{3x}{r_0} \frac{r_0}{2r_p} \right)} \right] \quad (2)$$

Here, x is the distance from the face and u_f is the radial displacement at the face according to equation 3.

$$u_f = u_{max} \frac{1}{3} e^{-0.15 \left(\frac{r_p}{r_0} \right)} \quad (3)$$

The 3D effect of the distance from the face can be simulated by coupling the LDP and GRC and applying a fictitious internal pressure in a 2D FEA that will result in the pre-convergence estimated by equation 2 prior to liner placement.

In this study, the effect of the segmental joints is modeled by the direct method as it gives a better representation of the joint behavior. The direct method reduces the joint stiffness depending on the magnitude of moments and thrust (normal force) at the joint location. The influence of longitudinal joints in the direct method is addressed by connecting the segments with elastic link elements. The critical elastic link is represented by the rotational stiffness as N.-A Do et al (2013) found that the axial and radial stiffness have a negligible effect on the segmental lining behavior. The properties of the longitudinal segmental joints are described in a form of moment-rotation relationship based on Leonhardt and Reimann (1966). This behavior of the segmental joints is significantly controlled by the normal force at the joint. With high normal force at the joint and low moments the joint remains closed with only compression pressure on the entire cross section. However, with high bending moment or small joint thickness, a gap will form when the pressure at the outer side becomes zero, leading to significant additional rotation. A moment-rotation behavioral model was described by Janssen (1983), divided into two portions. The first portion is a linear moment-rotation relationship (equation 3) describing the behavior before the joint gap is opened. The second portion is a non-linear relationship following the opening of the gap (equation 4).

$$linear: \left\{ \phi = \frac{Mh}{EI} = 12 \frac{M}{Eh^2b} \right\} \quad M < \frac{1}{6} F_n h \quad \phi < \frac{2F_n}{Ehb} \quad (3)$$

$$non - linear: \left\{ \phi = \frac{8F_n}{9bhE \left(\frac{2M}{F_n h} - 1 \right)} \right\} \quad M < \frac{1}{6} F_n h \quad \phi \geq \frac{2F_n}{Ehb} \quad (4)$$

In this study, the rotational stiffness is applied by a multi-linear yield function formulated by a rotational spring. The spring constant was defined by the moment-rotation angle relationship calculated according to equations 3 and 4, and is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Bending moment – joint rotation relationship of the longitudinal joint

The general configuration of the 2D models is presented in figure 4 for cross section 2. Each tunnel has an excavation diameter of 6.5 m with an annulus gap of 22.5 cm. The lining is modeled with embedded linear beam elements equal to the full 25 cm thickness of the segments. The distance between the tunnel center lines is 12 m (1.85 diameters), and the depth to springline is 4.9 to 6.1 diameters. The 2D model size is 139 m in the transverse direction and extends 24 m under the tunnel SL with a total of 4700 elements. Symmetry is not used so that the influence of sequential tunnel excavations can be investigated. The ground was modeled as elastic perfectly plastic with a Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion. The boundary conditions were set as fixed in the horizontal direction at the sides and fixed in both directions at the bottom (figure 4). For the simulation of the construction process in the zero pre-convergence models, three stages have been carried out: (1) an initial state of undisturbed ground under gravity conditions (geostatic loading); (2) the removal of the excavation material (6.25 m diameter), installation of the lining, and change of the material in the annular gap to hard grout; and (3) a repeat of stage 2 for the second bored tunnel.

For the simulation of pre-convergence, the CCM was implemented for each tunnel before lining installation, followed by modeling the time dependent pressures and properties of the annulus grout summarized in table 2. In each pre-convergence model, 9 stages have been performed. Stage 1 was performed as described above, followed by: (Stage 2) The first pre-convergence stage- removal of the excavation material and the annulus gap material, application of increased confinement pressure corresponding to the displacement anticipated at the section of the face of excavation according to equation 2 incorporating the recorded TBM pressure. (Stage 3) The second pre-convergence stage- reduction of the confinement pressure corresponding to the displacement at the shield tail 1.4 diameters (9 m) behind the tunnel face. (Stage4) installation of the lining and annulus grout material with the properties of fresh grout, and application of the grout pressure acting on both the lining and the excavation boundary. (Stage 5) removal of grout pressure; (stages6-8) repeat stages 2-4 for the excavation of the second tunnel with hardening of the annulus grout of the first tunnel in stage 5 to its final strength. (Stage 8) removal of grout pressure, and (stage 9) the hardening of the second tunnel annulus grout.

Figure 4. The 2D plane strain model used for the calculation of cross section 2.

Table 2. Support materials properties.

Material	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Poisson ratio	Unit weight (kN/m ³)
Lining concrete	34,000	0.2	24
Fresh Grout	50	0.2	12
Hard grout	1000	0.2	12

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

At cross section 1 (see Figure 1), the two instrumented rings were installed in the first tunnel (NB) excavated. Figure 5 shows the development of thrust forces and bending moments as a function of days from ring installation. Strain gage measurement collection began 64 days after ring installation, and 76 days prior to excavation of the adjacent (SB) tunnel. Strain gage measurement continued for 200 days after SB tunnel construction at this cross section but are shown only up to 30 days beyond the second tunnel pass, when the excavation face is more than 40 diameters beyond the monitored section. In figure 5 and 6b the thrust force measured at the invert shows a significantly higher value than at the measured points at the spring line and shoulders. This observation correlates with the geotechnical data report indicating that the bottom half of the tunnel was constructed in glacially overridden clay with $K_0 > 1$, and the top half of the tunnel was constructed through granular soil with $K_0 < 1$ (figure 1). While thrust forces show only a slight change of 2-4% (except at the spring line at the opposite side of the twin tunnel that shows a 26% increase) as a result of the second TBM passing the monitored section, the bending moments show a change of 18-22%, between 10 days prior to the second TBM pass when the distance was greater than 20 diameters to 30 days after the TBM passed where the distance was greater than 60 diameters past and after the annulus grout had hardened.

Figure 5. Cross section 1 thrust forces and bending moment development vs time in days from ring erection.

5.1. Force development in the first tunnel

Figures 6a and 6b show a comparison of the results at the first tunnel at cross section 1 after first tunnel construction and prior to second tunnel construction. For each numerical calculation two stages are displayed: the first stage is after the excavation and support of only the single tunnel, and the second stage is after the excavation and support of the second tunnel constructed at a distance of $2D$ between axes. A better correlation between the magnitude of the moments developed in the no pre-convergence calculations to the field measurements is seen in figure 6a. However, the shape of the moment diagram of the CCM model matches better with all 4 moment measurements collected from the field. This significant difference in the shape of the moment diagram between the no pre-convergence model and the CCM model, which is almost a mirror image, can be attributed to the lateral earth pressure ratio that is different than unity ($K_0 \neq 1$) and hydrostatic chamber pressure of the TBM (only linearly changing with depth). This difference in stress ratio results in different rates of relaxation at the crown and side wall in the CCM model. Before the lining is installed, the lower earth pressure balances the excavation and the ground relaxes slightly, while the high earth pressure relaxes more (whether located in the crown or spring line depending on the lateral earth pressure ratio). After the lining is installed, the lining feels more loading. This difference in relaxation ratios in the CCM model and the no pre-convergence model results in a different moment diagram and in lower internal lining forces.

Figure 6. Cross section 1 in the first tunnel: (a) Bending moment (kN*m/m) and (b) Thrust force (kN/m) diagrams after first tunnel excavation, and prior to second tunnel excavation.

After the excavation of the second tunnel, the field measurements show an increase in the 3 positive moment measurements by 16-18% and a decrease in the negative moment measurement by 28%. The effects of the excavation and support of the second tunnel can be observed in the CCM model as the relaxation during the excavation process results in a significant increase in bending moments with very close correlation to three of the four measured bending moment values. In the no per-convergence model, the maximum values of bending moment change by a similar magnitude observed in the field measurements, i.e., 8-20% at the side adjacent to the second tunnel but at the opposite side the change is only 1-5%.

From the comparison of the thrust forces in figure 6b, the increase in thrust force at the invert in both numerical models and in the field measurement corroborates with the high lateral in-situ stress loading from the glacially overridden clay layer crossed only at the bottom of the tunnel cross section (figure 1). The field measurement points to a high degree of relaxation with values closer to the CCM model and the relaxation analytical solution. The CCM model and the field measurements show a similar increase in force as a result of the second tunnel excavation while in the no pre-convergence model a reduction in thrust is seen.

5.2. Force development after second tunnel excavation

Only the first tunnel was monitored at cross section 1, while at cross section 2, both tunnels were monitored: one ring in the NB tunnel that was excavated first and two rings at the SB tunnel that was excavated second. Unfortunately, data collection began 50 days after the second tunnel passed the monitored cross section. Strain gage measurement continued for 390 days beyond SB tunnel construction at this cross section. The values shown in figures 7 and 8 are taken at 55 days after the second TBM pass having a distance greater than 20 diameters and hardened annulus grout.

In figure 8a and 8b the thrust force measured at the crown show a significantly higher value than at the measured points at the spring line and invert. This observation correlates with the geotechnical data report indicating that the tunnel crown was constructed through glacially overridden till with $K_0 > 1$, underlain by a 1.5 m thick silty fine sand layer followed by a coarser grained layer with $K_0 < 1$ continuing down more than 3 diameters under the tunnel invert, see figure 1.

As was seen in cross section 1, figure 7a shows the CCM model results provide a very good prediction of the bending moments in the first tunnel after the excavation of the second tunnel, while the no pre-convergence model shows slightly higher bending moments but a very different moment diagram. In figure 7b the moment diagram of the second tunnel shows a high correlation with the CCM model for both the values and diagram. In figure 8a and 8b a similar thrust diagram is observed in both tunnels with high correlation at the crown and invert between the field measurements and the no pre-convergence model. This corroborates with the expected high thrust force at the crown as the tunnel crosses a glacially overridden till layer with high lateral in-situ stress at the top part of the tunnel.

Figure 7. Bending moment (kN*m/m) diagrams at cross section 2.

Figure 8. Thrust force (kN/m) diagram at cross section 2.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented a comparison of 2D plane strain numerical calculations with and without the use of convergence-confinement method (CCM) principles. The results of the analysis are validated with bending moment and thrust force estimates made from field strain gage measurements during the Northgate Link project in Seattle. From this series of analysis the following conclusions are drawn:

- The loads developed in the case of a single tunnel show a better correlation of the moment diagram between the CCM 2D plain strain model and the field measurements, only with a lower magnitude of bending moments and thrust forces. As the second tunnel is excavated, causing an increase in the loads on the first tunnel, close agreement is observed between the CCM model and field measured internal forces.
- For the second tunnel excavated, close agreement is observed in bending moments measured and estimated with the CCM model, however, the CCM model thrust forces are lower than field measured. This indicates a lower degree of relaxation than predicted by the longitudinal displacement profile (LDP) and taking in account the TBM support pressure and a higher degree of relaxation than calculated in the no pre-relaxation model.
- The calculation of the internal lining forces without taking into account pre-convergence is commonly perceived as conservative in that it typically results in higher bending moments and thrust forces. This combination of a high bending moment with high axial force is in fact unconservative, as the real thrust forces that develop can be 50% lower while the bending moments essentially remain the same in magnitude. This in some situations can lead to the moments approaching or exceeding the thrust-moment (N-M) capacity envelope.

Although some may believe that a simplified analysis that neglects the effects of relaxation is a more conservative design approach, this may not be the case. The correct use of the CCM methodology for segmental lining design can result in less uncertainty and potentially allow for lower safety factors for design.

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